

ATTENTION TO CULTURE AND RECREATION PARKS

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ABSTRACT

Since the years of independence, many cultural and educational entertainment parks and avenues have been established for our people, and this article will talk about them.

People is always in motion and always in search, studies, works, in short, never rests. People usually takes time off once a week. It is at this time that culture and recreational parks, various centers enter the soul of people. In our country, many entertainment avenues and recreational parks have been built throughout the country to spend their free time in a meaningful way. has been continuing its work until First of all, when a person is tired of life's worries and chores, he writes down his heart in family problems, that is, he goes to the above-mentioned avenues and parks to write down his feelings, which are full of life's difficulties conducts. In the following years of independence, a number of new cultural and recreational parks are being built. For example, on March 21, 2014, the "Lokomotiv" culture and recreation park was launched in Mirzo Ulugbek district of Tashkent city. The new garden was established on the site of the former Zafar Diyar garden. Earlier, by the decision of the Tashkent city administration on December 5, 2012, the cultural and recreational park named after Zafar Diyor was leased to Lokomotiv Recreational Park LLC. Here is one piece of information: 12 cultural and recreational parks are currently operating in Tashkent. Eight of them are under the control of the Culture and Management Department of the Tashkent city administration. Gardens named after Abdulla Qodiriy and "Tashkentland" are owned by the Ministry of Internal Affairs and the Ministry of Foreign Economic Relations, respectively, while the gardens named after Zafar Diyor and Furqat are leased to various commercial organizations for a long term. On August 8, 2016, a new "AnhorLokomotiv" cultural and recreational park was opened in Tashkent. The garden with an area of 8 hectares is located on the banks of the "Anhor" canal, between Labzak and Zulfiyakhanim streets of Shaikhontohur district. There is a restaurant, several canteens, musical and illuminated fountains, children's playgrounds, as well as a summer cinema for 320 people on its territory. It also has special attractions that are unique in the city. The longest kart track and game center, the only one in the CIS countries, was also built on its closed territory. At the same time, visitors to the park can see miniature models of 7 attractions of 10 0 Uzbekistan: the Kalta-minor of Khiva, the Sherdor madrasa in Samarkand, the Tower-i Kalon in Bukhara, of the Andijan Babur memorial

complex, the Museum of the Timurids, the Tashkent chimes and Tashkent TV tower. A large 40-meter long musical fountain was built on the "Anhor" beach, which can spray water up to a height of 50 meters. Also, cultural and recreational parks are operating in all regions. In particular, in 1884, the cultural and recreation park named "Z.M. Babur" was founded in the city of Namangan, the center of Namangan region. Until 1990, A.S. Named after Pushkin. Based on the visits of the first President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, I. A. Karimov to Namangan city, and the decision No. 1170 of 2009, the park was included in the state program, redesigned in 2009, and the reconstruction work was started in October of the same year. 26 substandard service facilities in the park were demolished.

The cost of the project is 4 billion. Out of 800 million sums, 3 billion 300 million sums of construction, assembly and improvement works were carried out. Today, the park has 6 teahouses and kitchens, 9 ice cream pavilions, a chess club, 27 modern attractions and many other entertainment facilities. 1.5 km of irrigation networks and 1 modern water pump are working in the territory of the park. An open Estrada square, an amphitheater for 400 spectators was built in the garden. 175 seats and 160 night lights are installed in the territory for the cultural recreation of the population. Busy and quiet areas are organized. Bog1 fully covers its expenses financially. In 2011 alone, 95,007 million sums of income were planned, and 96,000 million sums of demand were fulfilled. From this, 64,000 million sums were earned from attractions and game devices in the park, and 32,000 million sums from rent and other income. Also, the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan of January 26, 2011, the implementation of the Control Plan on ensuring the implementation of the "Program of measures to improve the material and technical base of cultural and recreational parks in 2011-2015 and to further improve their activities". in order to ensure the control plan of the regional governor in February 2011 was developed and approved and delivered to the places for implementation. In particular, targeted regional programs have been developed and approved by city and district mayorals for capital reconstruction, capital repair and equipping of cultural and recreation parks in the region with modern attractions. A total of 13 cultural and recreational parks in Namangan region were reconstructed according to the program in 2011-2015 according to the plans specified in Annex 2 of the decision.

In particular, in 2011, the city of Namangan Z.M. The cultural and recreational park named after Babur, the youth park "Kamolot" in Namangan city, and the cultural and recreational park in Yangigorglon district were completely reconstructed. In 2012, Dostlik park in Mingbulok district and Furqat in Chortoq district were renovated. culture and recreation parks named after were included in the capital reconstruction program and were implemented. In 2013, the "Independence" park of Uychi district and the "Yettibuloq" park of Namangan district were reconstructed according to the program. In 2014, culture and recreation parks in Torakorgan, Kosonsoy and Uchkorgon districts were reconstructed within the framework of the program. In Uzbekistan, cultural and recreational parks vary depending on the size, historical appearance and natural conditions of the city area. In small cities there is one, in big cities several, and in cities with a population of more than 500,000, in addition to parks of city-wide significance, each district in the city can have a cultural and recreational park. Cultural service to the population is given a high place in it. Resolution No. 322 of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated December 29, 2010 "On approval of

the program of measures to strengthen the material and technical base of cultural and recreational parks in 2011-2015 and to further improve the activities of the park” . In short, regardless of the period of historical development of the culture and recreation park, it has contributed to the development of human consciousness through cultural recreation. The period of independence in the Republic of Uzbekistan led to the fulfillment of this task at the level of the requirements of the new era, and the cultural and recreational parks acquired a special meaning and appearance. In conclusion, the fact that there are such unique entertainment venues in our country is doing its happy service for all our people to remember very pleasant feelings and organize their leisure time in a meaningful way.

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